

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Value statement template

Full resource

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Introduction

Summary

This template is for specifying and documenting the values on which your research assessment process is based, and it is to be filled out by relevant persons when starting a research assessment (RA) process. Relevant persons may vary depending on the assessment process and type of organization.

Identifying and approving values determines the purpose and context of a RA process. Values affect also used assessment methods, metrics and indicators referred as assessment protocol. Therefore, it is recommended to explore also other SCOPE+i Resources such as:

- Guide on choosing an assessment method <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to open science (OS). Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this template supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This template is most relevant for stage S.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Super-values, values and sub-values

Defining values is an important aspect of a “value-led” RA process, and a quite complicated SCOPE stage. Values are the starting point for all kinds of assessment and evaluation processes. OS and EDI (equity, diversity and inclusion) dimensions are values as such. The purpose of an assessment process, methods, used indicators etc. highly reflect values - and vice versa, e.g. values guide in finding the right indicators.

According to the SCOPE full guide, a value is “a judgement made about what is important” (International Network of Research Management Societies - Research Evaluation Group 2023, p. 8). However, the guide recognises three different layers of values (Table 1), the consideration of which supports getting to the heart of what is valued about a particular entity, and should therefore be the target of evaluation:

Table 1. Super-values, values and sub-values by the International Network of Research Management Societies - Research Evaluation Group (2023).

Super-values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are at the highest level, are often stated as single words (e.g., openness, diversity, inclusivity), and - can be useful in steering an evaluation, - but lack the level of detail to be used in the design of an evaluation
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are at the next level down, and - they can be understood by asking how the super-value manifests itself: these are the things you want to evaluate
Sub-values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are at the lowest level of granularity - these are what your values “look and feel like” - can be understood as something that indicates values (i.e. the things you want to evaluate) and therefore guide in finding the right indicators

In some evaluation contexts higher level values would suffice (INORMS, 2021 and 2023).

Useful reading e.g. Science Europe. (2023). Recognising What We Value: Recommendations on Recognition Systems, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858100>.

Template for defining your values statements

In the following table, fill in the values of the ongoing RA process. Add as more rows into the table as needed. Maintain a hierarchy according to the weighting of values when you fill in the table. If you prefer copy-paste the actual value statement template part of this document in a new blank document leaving other parts of the document out. Go back to Table 1 to get started if needed.

Super-values	Values	Sub-values	Value specification
e.g. diversity	e.g. diversity of careers	e.g. valuing diversity in promotions to senior and manager positions	e.g. all actions that promote diversity related to gender, age, ethnic, national or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, language, disability, political opinion, social or economic condition

References

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

INORMS SCOPE workshop case study. University of Glasgow: Supporting the careers of others. May 2021, In [inorms-scope-workshop-case-study-university-of-glasgow-final.pdf](#), cited 13.1.2025

Appendix: Examples on how to define super-values, values and sub-values

Start by defining super-values e.g. by exploring Picture 1 (below). Complete by embedding values and sub-values in the form of a sentence or statement.

Example 1:

- Super-value: Diversity
- Value: Recognizing the diversity of contributions
- Sub-value: Assessment protocols respecting both the diversity of outputs and diversity of practices

Example 2:

- Super-value: Openness
- Value: Valorisation and recognising more types of open research activities
- Sub-value: Raising the profile of publication practices such as open peer-reviews

Figure 2. Examples of super-values.

